

COMPARING THE LOCAL PREDICTIONS OF THE STRAIN ENERGY RELEASE RATE BY CZM AND VCCT IN LARGE AND CURVED DELAMINATIONS

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ABSTRACT

The two most common numerical methods to predict delaminations in composite laminates are the Cohesive Zone Model (CZM) and the Virtual Crack Closure Technique (VCCT). The available literature on the topic has shown comparable performance for CZM and VCCT, but is limited to the comparison of global descriptors, like the load-displacement curve. A local comparison is thus still lacking, especially for large and curved delamination fronts, for which more significant differences are expected. This work thus aims to compare the predictions of CZM and VCCT considering the local calculations of the strain energy release rate G and its components. To address this, we simulated the response of a special reinforced end-notch flexure specimen featuring a curved delamination front. A reference CZM simulation was first performed; since G is not an immediate output of cohesive elements, a J-integral formulation was implemented in this simulation. Delamination fronts were then extracted at different damage levels and then mapped in VCCT simulations. A smoothing algorithm was successfully adopted to compensate the discontinuities due to the discontinuous nature of VCCT. The comparison showed that both methods predicted similar trends in G and its mode I, mode II, and mode III components, but significant differences were observed in absolute values. Overall, this work presents a comparison methodology for the comparison of VCCT and CZM predictions, overcoming the previous limitations of both approaches.

1 INTRODUCTION

Delaminations is a critical failure mode of composite laminates. Predicting it is thus crucial in the safe design of composite structures. The two most commonly adopted numerical approaches for this task are the Cohesive Zone Model (CZM) and the Virtual Crack Closure Technique (VCCT) [1-2]. The former relies on the use of cohesive elements, that are special purpose elements whose constitutive law is in the form of a traction-separation law. Through a damage variable, CZM can model the fracture process zone ahead of the delamination front. Conversely, VCCT is a linear elastic fracture mechanics approach, and does not model any process zone.

Several work in the literature compare the performance of both approaches and under different loading conditions, including static and fatigue loading [1-4]. However, this comparison is often performed at a global scale using global descriptors, most commonly the load-displacement curve. While this allows a first comparison, it provides only limited insights into the capabilities of the two approaches. Moreover, it prevents an understanding of the causes of any possible discrepancy. A more accurate and deep analysis would compare the calculations of the strain energy release rate G at the delamination front, and how G is decomposed in the different modes of fractures. However, this was so far prevented for the following causes:

1. G is not a direct output of the CZM [5-7];
2. The CZM does not make a distinction between mode II and mode III [5-7];

3. The VCCT is often affected by discontinuities and concentrations of G for large and curved crack fronts [8].

This work presents a procedure to overcome these limitations and compare the local readings of G and its components by the CZM and the VCCT. The first two limitations above are overcome by adopting a J-integral formulation of the cohesive elements. The third limitation is addressed by adopting a smoothing algorithm for the description of the delamination front. A large partially reinforced End-Notched Flexure (ENF) specimen was used as study case, since it features large and curved delamination fronts.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Numerical case-study

Abaqus 2024 was used in all the numerical simulations [9]. Figure 1a shows the partially reinforced ENF specimen considered, which was previously introduced in [6]. It is composed by two 140 mm x 60 mm x 1.5 mm composite plates, featuring an initial 40 mm delamination. Two reinforcing arms, of dimensions 85 mm x 25 mm x 1.5 mm, are bonded on both the top and bottom sides of the ENF: these promote a curved delamination front that evolves during loading.

Figure 1: a) The ENF model adopted in this work; b) a triangular traction-separation law.

A vertical displacement is imposed in the front edge of the specimen. Following [6], the material properties of both laminates (large arms and reinforcing arms) and those of the interface are reported in Table 1. In the table, G_{Ic} , G_{IIc} and G_{IIIc} are the mode I, mode II and mode III fracture toughnesses, respectively, while η is the BK law exponent [10]. Note that these toughnesses are used only in the CZM simulations, while the VCCT simulations employ virtually infinite toughnesses (see Section 2.2). For the CZM simulations, bilinear traction-separation laws are considered and described by the stiffnesses K_I , K_{II} and K_{III} and the maximum stresses τ_I , τ_{II} and τ_{III} in mode I, mode II and mode III, respectively. Note that these stresses are adopted to cause an extended process zone: although less realistic, this would better highlight the main differences between VCCT and CZM and facilitate the extraction of the different delamination fronts.

Table 1: Laminate and interface property adopted [6].

Laminate elastic properties					
E_{11} (GPa)	$E_{22} = E_{33}$ (GPa)	$G_{12} = G_{13}$ (GPa)	G_{23} (GPa)	$\nu_{12} = \nu_{13}$ (-)	ν_{23} (-)
154	8.5	4.2	3.036	0.35	0.4
Interface properties for all simulations			Traction-separation law parameters		
G_{Ic} (kJ/m ²)	$G_{IIc} = G_{IIIc}$ (kJ/m ²)	η (-)	τ_I (MPa)	$\tau_{II} = \tau_{III}$ (MPa)	$K_I = K_{II} = K_{III}$ (N/mm ³)
0.3	3	2	35	35	10^5

The mesh size in the area of the delamination front was always kept equal to 1 mm or below; in the other regions it was increased for computational efficiency, but it was never higher than 5 mm. For the CZM simulations, solid C3D8I elements were used for all laminates, with three elements in the thickness direction; zero-thickness cohesive elements were used via an UEL subroutine developed in [7]. For the

VCCT simulations, continuum shell SC8R were used for all laminates, with one element in the thickness direction; the standard VCCT interaction of Abaqus was considered [9].

2.2 Adopted approach

A meaningful comparison of the CZM and VCCT readings of G would require the same delamination front and the same imposed displacement. To this end, a first reference CZM simulation was performed with a maximum applied displacement of 30 mm. This simulation was performed considering the initial delaminated 40 mm. As mentioned in Section 1, G is not a direct output of the CZM and a decomposition between mode II and mode III cannot be obtained. Therefore, the J-integral approach developed and implemented in [7] is adopted for the CZM simulation: through the identification of the delamination growth direction, this approach can compute all three G components in a simulation featuring cohesive elements.

The reference CZM simulation thus allows to identify a process zone, defined as:

$$0 < d_e = \frac{\omega_d}{G_c} < 1 \quad (1)$$

where d_e is the energy damage and ω_d is the dissipated energy (both quantities are defined in the traction-separation law reported in Figure 1b). In [7], the iso-damage lines were considered as perpendicular to the delamination growth direction. Therefore, in this work, these are extracted from the CZM process zone and used as delamination fronts for the VCCT simulations. In particular, for specific increments of the CZM simulation, five delamination fronts are extracted corresponding to a damage variable d_e equal to 0, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75 and 1.

These delamination fronts are thus described via the nodes whose damage variable d_e is closer to these values. This, however, causes a discontinuous description of the delamination front, since the mesh is not conformal to the shape of the front. As a result, strain energy release rate concentrations arise in corner nodes; moreover, in these nodes, the directions of mode II and mode III propagation cannot be distinguished [6-7]. This issue is even more critical for the ELS considered in this work, since it is characterised by a very large and curved crack front [8]. Therefore, the coordinates of the nodes composing the delamination front were smoothed using a moving average algorithm with window size of 15. The smoothed coordinates are then mapped to a the VCCT simulation to create the delamination front. Finally, the VCCT simulations can be run with the smoothed delamination front extracted from the CZM simulation: note that, for these simulations, an infinite fracture toughness is considered to prevent propagation and allow the readings of G . A simple schematic of the procedure is reported in Figure 2.

Figure 2: the adopted comparative procedure.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 3a shows the load-displacement curve obtained from the CZM simulation. As shown, we have selected two increments on this curve for the present analysis, corresponding to specific values of applied displacement and resulting load. These were selected to ensure the delamination front propagated enough to allow a meaningful comparison. The delamination fronts extracted for both points are reported in Figure 3b and Figure 3c. The delamination fronts of the Figure 3b increment are close to the beginning of the reinforcing arm: the fronts are relatively straight, with some curves starting to form towards lower values of damage. Conversely, the delamination fronts relative to Figure 3c are well developed below the reinforcing arm, being significantly more curved.

Figure 3: a) load displacement curve of the simulated ELS and b-c) delamination fronts at different increments of the CZM simulation.

The calculated strain energy release rate components by both the VCCT and the CZM (through the implemented J-integral formulation) are reported in Figure 4 and Figure 5 for the delamination fronts reported in Figure 3a and Figure 3b, respectively. Overall, the two techniques seem to lead to similar trends but generally different results.

Regarding Figure 4, the discrepancies between the different fronts appear significant. In particular, the VCCT calculates very high values of the strain energy release rate, especially for the fronts with the higher damage. This higher discrepancy can be explained by the fact that the higher damage fronts are located below the front edge of the reinforcing arms (see Figure 3b). One of the fundamental assumptions of the VCCT is that the propagation of the front is self-similar. The sudden thickness variation cause by the presence of the reinforcing arms makes this assumption not applicable, since the crack propagation is locally altered by the increased thickness and thus stiffness. Indeed, for the lower damage fronts, this effect seems mitigated. This is interesting, since these fronts are more curved than the higher damage ones (see Figure 3b): the thickness variation thus seems to have a stronger effect than the curvature of the delamination fronts.

Figure 4: a-e) The calculated components of the strain energy release rate by both the VCCT and the CZM for the five delamination fronts of Figure 3b.

Figure 5 shows, instead, a much closer agreement between the two tested methods. In this case, VCCT and CZM show more similar results for the higher damage fronts. In all cases, the highest discrepancy is observed for the GIII peak in correspondence of about 15 mm of the y-coordinate. Considering the mode III direction, thus parallel to the delamination front, this is also a location of thickness variation still due to the presence of a reinforcing arms' bounding edge (see Figure 3c). Both this discrepancy and the general better agreement seem to confirm that the reinforcing arms affect the accuracy of the VCCT.

In all cases, discrepancies are always observed in at least one of the components of G . Moreover, the discrepancies between the methods seem to be independent between each other, which implies that the total strain energy release rate G_{tot} , the sum of the components, is also calculated differently. Therefore, the discrepancies are not due different decomposition in the modes of fracture.

Figure 5: a-e) The calculated components of the strain energy release rate by both the VCCT and the CZM for the five delamination fronts of Figure 3c.

4 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORKS

This work presented a comparative analysis on the strain energy release rate (G) calculation by the VCCT and the CZM. The two techniques were already compared earlier, but always at a global level, while in this work their local capabilities are investigated. The considered study-case is a reinforced ENF specimen, which causes large and curved delamination fronts.

A specific procedure was thus developed. First, a CZM simulation is run using a J-integral algorithm to compute G at the delamination front from the cohesive elements. For two simulation increments, five delamination fronts were extracted corresponding to damages equal to 0, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75 and 1. These fronts are then smoothed with a moving average algorithm, as their discontinuous nature would prevent correct readings from the VCCT. The smoothed coordinates of the fronts are then mapped onto a new simulation to be run with the VCCT.

All the tested delamination fronts highlighted some level of discrepancy. In particular, the thickness variations caused by the reinforcing arms seemed to be the main source of inaccuracy from the VCCT: indeed, such thickness variations violate the VCCT assumption of a self-similar crack propagation. Conversely, the curvature of the delamination fronts does not seem to cause significant discrepancies: this further confirms the importance of the smoothing algorithm that allows a mesh conformal to the delamination front.

The work investigated mainly two increments of the ENF specimen, which is mainly loaded in mode II and mode III. Further investigations are planned, involving more increments of the ENF as well as the study of a reinforced Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) specimen. The reinforced DCB would allow a mode I comparison, thus extending the scope of this work, but also give a more informed feedback, since experimental results are available for the reinforced DCB. Moreover, the comparison presented in this work is performed considering an extended process zone to better distinguish the different fronts. Considering that the process zone is a key difference between VCCT and CZM, performing this comparison with more realistic process zones is an important future planned work.

REFERENCES

- [1] J.A. Pascoe, R.C. Alderliesten, R. Benedictus, Methods for the prediction of fatigue delamination growth in composites and adhesive bonds – A critical review, *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, **112**, 2013, pp. 72-96.
- [2] M. Heidari-Rarani, M- Sayedain, Finite element modeling strategies for 2D and 3D delamination propagation in composite DCB specimens using VCCT, CZM and XFEM approaches, *Theoretical and Applied Fracture Mechanics*, **103**, 2019, 102246.
- [3] A. Pirondi, G. Giugliese, F. Moroni, A. Bernasconi, A. Jamil, Comparative Study of Cohesive Zone and Virtual Crack Closure Techniques for Three-Dimensional Fatigue Debonding, *The Journal of Adhesion*, **90**, 2014, pp. 457-481.
- [4] R. Liu, Z. Yu, F. Nasonov, Evaluations on VCCT and CZM methods of delamination propagation simulation for composite specimens, *Aerospace systems*, **6**, 2023, pp. 621-632.
- [5] A. Turon, P.P. Camanho, J. Costa, C.G. Davila, A damage model for the simulation of delamination in advanced composites under variable-mode loading, *Mechanics of materials*, **38**, 2006, pp. 1072-1089.
- [6] L. Carreras, B.L.V. Bak, A. Turon, J. Renart, E. Lindgaard, Point-wise evaluation of the growth driving direction for arbitrarily shaped delamination fronts using cohesive elements, *European Journal of Mechanics / A Solids*, **72**, 2018, pp. 464-482.
- [7] L. Carreras, E. Lindgaard, J. Renart, B.L.V. Bak, A. Turon, An evaluation of mode-decomposed energy release rates for arbitrarily shaped delamination fronts using cohesive elements, *Computer methods in Applied Mechanical Engineering*, **347**, 2019, pp. 218-237.
- [8] L.M. Martulli, A. Bernasconi, J. Renart, B.L.V. Bak, A. Turon, An efficient and versatile use of the VCCT for composites delamination growth under fatigue loadings in 3D numerical analysis: the Sequential Static Fatigue algorithm, *International Journal of Fatigue*, **170**, 2023, 107493.
- [9] Dassault Systemès. Abaqus 2024 manual.
- [10] M.L. Benzeggagh and M. Kenane, Measurement of mixed-mode delamination fracture toughness of unidirectional glass/epoxy composites with mixed-mode bending apparatus, *Composite Science and Technology*, **56**, 1996, pp. 439-449.